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D5.10 Final impact maximisation and sustainability guidelines

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Abstract	This report provides support for CS projects' tema that wish to use the ACTION impact assessment methodology. It conveys information that is also included in the ACTION toolkit.
Keywords	Social impact, economic impact, scientific impact, environmental impact, political impact, impact assessment methodology

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is for Citizen Science projects' teams interested in learning how to use and adapt to their need the ACTION impact assessment methodology. It provides a how-to-guide to use the resources developed and successfully tested during the ACTION project.

More specifically, the reader will find in this document step by step suggestions on how to use the ACTION impact assessment canvas in selecting the most relevant impacts of their project; the impact assessment matrix so to define when to conduct data gathering activities and who to involve in it and, finally the questionnaires to be used or adapted to this purposes.

This document provides also links to the resources developed for supporting citizen science projects' sustainability and it is complementary with the ACTION toolkit available on the project website: <https://actionproject.eu/toolkit/>

1 INTRODUCTION

This document offers guidelines to the CS projects' teams that are willing to use, or adapt, the ACTION impact assessment methodology. It can be considered a how-to guide and it is complementary with the ACTION CS toolkit. Indeed, the information here reported, is also included in the ACTION toolkit, even if in a slightly different form.

Assessing the impact of a CS project is important in many ways. First of all, thinking about the desired impact of a project helps in better planning the project itself so that activities are designed looking at the maximisation of the desired impact since its beginning. Secondly, assessing the impact on a regular basis in different stages of a project, can help the team to improve the project activities so as to serve as a reflexivity tool. Finally, impact assessment can help to better communicate to project stakeholders (including decision makers, founders and the volunteers engaged) the benefits produced by the project, assure accountability and promote additional, related activities if needed.

The ACTION impact assessment methodology considers five areas of impact: scientific, social, economic, political and environmental. Besides this, it supports projects in understanding their transformative potential, i.e. the degree to which the project can help to change, alter, or replace current systems, the business-as-usual in one or more fields such as knowledge production or environmental protection.

The methodology is designed to be modular and flexible, in order to be adaptable to the specific characteristics of different CS projects. Indeed, not all the impact dimensions considered are (equally) relevant for all projects, depending on their nature, their specific focus and the level of citizen engagement. A full description of the methodology is provided in Passani, A. et al. (2020), *Impact assessment methodological framework v1*

The document is structured as follows: the next section presents the ACTION impact assessment canvas and how to use it, then the impact assessment matrix is presented and finally guidelines on how to use the questionnaires developed and tested during the ACTION project are provided. Section three recaps the work done on sustainability and provides instructions on where to go for additional resources on this topic. In the conclusion section instructions on how to get further support on impact assessment of CS projects are provided.

2 Main steps in assessing the impact of a CS project

The process for assessing the impact of a CS project works as follows:

1. Define the project outputs, stakeholders and relevance of various impact areas and dimensions. This can be done by using the [ACTION impact assessment canvas](#): a four page graphic form, accompanied by [guidelines](#) supporting projects in filling it in.
2. Define an impact assessment process, and when and how to collect the required data. Projects can use the ACTION [impact assessment matrix](#), which lists the different variables for each of the impact dimensions, and advises who needs to supply the data (project managers and/or citizens/volunteers), and when (only at the end of the project (ex-post), or also at the beginning (ex-ante)).
3. Gather data. This can be done by using [questionnaires](#) developed and successfully tested in ACTION.
4. Analyse the data and draft a report. This can be done in different ways considering the audience to be addressed. If looking at the scientific community, an example has been developed [for the Students, air pollution and DIY sensing pilot in ACTION](#). If considering different audiences simultaneously (including citizens and decision makers), a shorter report can be developed. Examples are available for each of the ACTION pilots in the ACTION final impact assessment deliverable available on the ACTION website and in the Resource section and also on Zenodo. Additionally, if considering a more visual approach to reporting, the [document](#) developed by In My BackYard, one of the ACTION pilots, can be an interesting source of inspiration. Finally, impact assessment results, along with a summary of the most relevant information on the project, can then be visualised in an infographic, such as the [ACTION Pilot's Dashboard](#).

In the following subsection each of the tools mentioned above is briefly described and additional guidelines are added

2.1 The ACTION impact assessment canvas

Ideally, the action impact assessment canvas should be filled in by the project team during the design/planning phase of the project or at the beginning of the project’s activities. If this is not possible, it can be filled in also at a later stage. It represents the first step for running the impact assessment of a project.

It is composed of four pages (reported here below). Guidelines on how to fill it are included in a [dedicated ppt](#), a video tutorial explaining how to use the canvas is also available here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fwz3_memBLw

<p style="text-align: center;">Key problem you want to address</p> <p>What social, economic, environmental problem are you trying to (contribute to) solve?</p> <p><i>Example: Air pollution, especially that generated by private vehicles, in Turin (Italy)</i></p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Key research question</p> <p>What is the main research question addressed by your CS project?</p> <p><i>Example: how does private mobility traffic impact on air quality in specific areas of the city and in specific moments of the day?</i></p>
<p>Key stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers <i>Representing which disciplines? Junior or senior?</i> • Citizen scientists <i>Do you foresee engaging any specific social group? Is your project working towards inclusiveness? What is the gender distribution in your group of citizens: female/male/not disclosed/other?</i> • Policy/decision makers <i>Are you targeting local/national or international policy/decision makers?</i> • Business actors <i>Will your project provide input to business actors? Are you collaborating with business actors as part of your project?</i> • Other organisations <i>Will you collaborate with other organisations? What kinds of organisations can benefit from the project’s activities/results?</i> • General public <i>Do you foresee reaching local, national or international audiences?</i> 	

<p style="text-align: center;">Input</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where are you starting from? • What was there before the beginning of the project? • What are the economic/technical and human resources you will use? How much do they cost? <p><i>Example: this project is the continuation of a previous one, we already have 200 CS engaged and 5 lead researchers</i></p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What will you do? • What do you do to engage your stakeholders? <p><i>Example: Air quality monitoring with low-cost DIY sensors. 5 events. 3 training workshops</i></p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the tangible results you expect to deliver? • How many people do you aim to engage? • How many people do you aim to reach through communication? • How many policy makers you expect to contact? <p><i>Example: a new version of our air quality measurement sensor; a curated dataset; 3 publications. 500 CS engaged. 1k citizens reached.</i></p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Short-terms and long-term impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What positive changes do you expect for your stakeholders? • Which areas of impact are more relevant? (see ACTION impact assessment framework in the next page and described in the related PPT) • Which dimensions are more relevant? (see ACTION impact assessment framework in the next page and described in the related PPT) <p><i>Example: citizens will be more aware of air quality, better informed on how to reduce their exposure, 10% will change their mobility behaviours. Policy makers will change mobility policies. Papers deeply up taken by researchers in the field.</i></p>

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Assign a value from 1 to 5 to each areas of impact and to the related dimensions
(1 is not relevant/we do not aspect impacts. - 5 is very relevant/will be a crucial impact)
Definitions of the areas of impact and related dimensions are in the PPT that accompany this canvas

	Value
Scientific impact	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Scientific knowledge	
New research fields and interdisciplinarity	
New knowledge resources	
Innovation in education	

	Value
Political impact	<i>Medium or media value</i>
Impact on policy process	
Political participation	
Self-governance	
Political support for citizen science	

	Value
Economic impact	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Impact on employment	
Cost saving	
Income and revenue generation for leading organisations	
Economic impact on the local communities	

	Value
Other impacts	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Please specify.....	
Please specify.....	

	Value
Social impact	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Community building and empowerment	
Social inclusion	
Researchers and research community's growth and empowerment	
Knowledge, skills and competences	
Changes in way of thinking, attitude and values	
Behavioural change	

	Value
Environmental	<i>Medium or median value</i>
Impact on ecosystem	
Impact on biodiversity	
Impact on soil quality	
Impact on water quality	
Impact on air quality	
Impact on health	

Figure 1: ACTION impact assessment canvas

2.2 The ACTION impact assessment matrix

The ACTION impact assessment matrix supports CS teams in better planning the data gathering activities needed for the impact assessment. In the matrix the reader will find the lists of the variables for each of the impact dimensions considered. For each variable it provides suggestions on who needs to supply the data (project managers and/or citizens scientists/volunteers) and when (only after the project ends - ex-post - or also at the beginning of the project- ex-ante). Of course, if the ex-ante analysis is not feasible (due to lack of time or resources or because at the beginning of the project the impact assessment activities were not yet planned) it is possible to proceed with the impact assessment at the end of the project (but with a slightly different questionnaire).

Engaging citizens/volunteers participating in the CS project, it is very important to know, directly from them, what are the benefits of their experiences thanks to the project. If engaging them is not possible, for example their engagement in the project is very limited in time or scope or, on the contrary, they have been already asked to carry out several activities for the project, it is also possible to rely only on the point of view of the CS managers. In this case, it is recommended to consider the needed information and gather it in alternative ways: using participant observation during the project activities or organizing short group interviews/focus groups as valid options.

The ACTION impact assessment matrix is available in the form on an online interactive map at the following link: https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_IChx0Ks/

For clarity and completeness we report the information also in table format here below.

Table 1: ACTION impact assessment matrix

Scientific impact			
Variable	Respondent	Ex-ante	Ex-post
<i>Knowledge in academia</i>			
Quantity of new data created (No of datapoints)	manager	no	yes
Quality of data in datasets	manager	no	yes
Research outputs' compliance with FAIR principles of open data.	manager	no	yes
Research outputs visibility on social media and research platforms (Academia, Research.edu, etc)	manager	no	yes
Citizen scientists' participation and recognition in the scientific output.	manager	no	yes
N. of publications (scientific and non-scientific)	manager	no	yes
<i>New research fields and interdisciplinarity</i>			
Self-reported interdisciplinarity	manager	no	yes
N. of new research groups created	manager	no	yes
Sub-disciplines emerging	manager	no	yes
<i>New knowledge resources</i>			
Ease access to knowledge that is otherwise hard to access	manager	no	yes
	citizens	no	yes
Facilitate knowledge creation among societal actors and groups	manager	no	yes
	citizens	no	yes

Development of new data-gathering tools	manager	no	yes
<i>Innovation in (academic) education</i>			
Innovation in academic or school curricula	manager	no	yes
Innovation in (other) educational/training methods	manager	no	yes
Social Impact			
Variable	Repondent	Ex-ante	Ex-post
<i>Community building and empowerment</i>			
N. of citizens scientists engaged in project activities	manager	no	yes
Role of the citizen scientists in the participatory research process	manager	no	yes
N. of awareness level/dissemination events organised	manager	no	yes
N. of participants to organised events	manager	no	yes
N. of persons/organisation reached trough social media	manager	no	yes
Level of interaction among citizen scientist	manager	no	yes
Changes in bonding social capital among citizen scientists	citizens	no	yes
Changes in bridging social capital among citizen scientists	citizens	no	yes
Changes in linking social capital	manager	no	yes
N. of new social relations established	citizens	no	yes
Increase in the perceived quality of social relations	citizens	no	yes
Self-assessment on project capability to influence trust among participants	manager	no	yes
Project self-assessment of its capacity to foster the creations and the enlargement of local communities/groups	manager	no	yes
Improvement in the self-perceived efficacy of citizen scientists	citizens	no	yes
<i>Social Inclusion</i>			
Percentage of participants belonging to underrepresented social groups	manager	no	yes
Ration among age groups of participants	citizens	yes	yes
Male/female share among participants	citizens	yes	yes
Diversity of participants in terms of education level	citizens	yes	yes
Diversity of participants in terms of income	citizens	yes	yes
Diversity of participants in terms of cultural differences	citizens	yes	yes
Diversity of participants in terms of value orientation (materialistic/post materialistic)	citizens	yes	yes
Presence and description of a dedicated strategy for social inclusion and diversity management	manager	no	yes
<i>Researchers and research community growth and empowerment</i>			
N. of new collaborations established with other researchers/research organisations	manager	no	yes
N. of new collaborations established with other organisations (excluding research organisations)	manager	no	yes
Changes in researchers' career path	manager	no	yes
Changes in researchers' level of trust for citizens, other CS managers and decision-makers	manager	no	yes
<i>Knowledge, skills and competences</i>			
N. of CS projects, or similar activities, in which participants have been enrolled/are enrolled	citizens	yes	yes
Probability to engage in CS projects in the future	citizens	no	yes
Participation in cause-oriented initiatives (see political impact)	citizens	yes	yes

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N. of participants considering a scientific or environmental-related carrier as a result of the project (for student only)	citizens	no	yes
N. of participants considering enrolling in life-learning educational program related to science or environmental studies (only for adults)	citizens	no	yes
Changes in the interest for the specific topic covered by the project	citizens	no	yes
Changes in the interest in science related topics and activities	citizens	no	yes
Changes in the understanding of the scientific method	citizens	no	yes
Changes in the understanding of the scientific process	citizens	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills in the research design-related activity	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills in the data gathering- related activities	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills in the data curation- related activities	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills in the data visualisation and analysis-related activities	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills in the data interpretation- related activities	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills on impact assessment	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills on citizen engagement			
Acquisition of new skills in communicating results	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills in the valorisation of project results for policy making	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills on project sustainability	manager	no	yes
Increment in technological literacy	manager	no	yes
Acquisition of new skills related to critical thinking	manager	no	yes
<i>Changes in way of thinking, attitude and values</i>			
Changes in way of thinking related to the specific topic of the project. Index to be selected/elaborated on a project-by-project base	citizens	yes	yes
Changes in way of thinking on environmental issues/concerns	citizens	yes	yes
Changes in the way of thinking on science	citizens		
<i>Behavioural change</i>			
Impact on green consumption behaviours	citizens	yes	yes
Impact on project-specific related behaviours	citizens	yes	yes
Economic impact			
Variable	Respondent	Ex-ante	Ex-post
<i>Impact on employment</i>			
n. of new job places created within the leading organisation	manager	no	yes
n. of participants that changed or got a new job as a result of the CS project	citizens	no	yes
<i>Cost saving</i>			
Average n. of hours dedicated to the project by volunteers	manager	no	yes
n. of hours dedicated to citizens' engagement and support	manager	no	yes
<i>Income and revenue generation</i>			
n. of new or improved product created	manager	no	yes
n. of new service created or improved	manager	no	yes
Revenue generated by each of the new or improved products	manager	no	yes
<i>Economic impact on the local community</i>			

<i>To be elaborated on a project-by-project base</i>			
Political impact			
Variable	Respondent	Ex-ante	Ex-post
<i>Impact on policy processes</i>			
N. of new/changed policies (e.g. regulatory, management or conservation actions)	manager	yes	yes
Agenda setting: n. of new policy discourses and problem definitions	manager	no	yes
Self-reported contribution to policy implementation and enforcement	manager	no	yes
Self-reported contribution to monitoring and evaluation of policy implementation	manager	no	yes
N. of meetings/conferences organised/attended for influencing policymakers	manager	no	yes
<i>Political participation</i>			
Political literacy: self-reported changes in the time spent by individuals in getting informed about political issues	manager	yes	yes
	citizens	yes	yes
Self-reported changes in engagement in political groups or activities (e.g. party membership, work for candidates, protesting, lobbying)	manager	yes	yes
	citizens	yes	yes
Self-reported changes in civic engagement (e.g. membership in voluntary associations, charities or environmental groups)	manager	yes	yes
	citizens	yes	yes
<i>Self-governance</i>			
Active involvement in or creation of self-managed spaces for DIY-science community projects	manager	yes	yes
	citizens	yes	yes
Active involvement in or creation of new civic society organisations and/or informal groups created at the local level	manager	yes	yes
	citizens	yes	yes
N. of political events (e.g. rallies) organised/attended for involving wider actors	manager	yes	yes
	citizens	yes	yes
<i>Political support for citizen science</i>			
Change in policy support and funding for citizen science	manager	yes	yes
N. of new partnerships between government decision-makers/policymakers and citizen science initiatives and organisations	manager	yes	yes
Environmental impact			
Variable	Respondent	Ex-ante	Ex-post
<i>Impact on ecosystem</i>			
Direct reduction emissions	manager	no	yes
Indirect reduction emissions	citizens	yes	yes
<i>Impact on biodiversity</i>			
Direct improvement biodiversity	manager	no	yes
Indirect improvement biodiversity	citizens	yes	yes
<i>Impact on soil quality</i>			
Direct improvement soil	manager	no	yes
Indirect improvement soil	citizens	yes	yes
<i>Impact on water quality</i>			
Direct improvement water	manager	no	yes
Indirect improvement water	citizens	yes	yes

<i>Impact on air quality</i>			
Direct improvement air quality	manager	no	yes
Indirect improvement air quality	citizens	yes	yes
<i>Impact on health</i>			
Direct influence health	manager	no	yes
Indirect influence health	citizens	yes	yes
Transformative impact			
	Respondent	Ex-ante	Ex-post
Transformative impact form	manager	yes	yes

2.3 ACTION impact assessment questionnaires

Thanks to the ACTION impact canvas a CS team can define the areas of impact and related dimensions that are more relevant for their project. Then, using the ACTION impact assessment matrix, it can plan the data gathering activities in terms of frequency and timing. Now, for each of the areas of impact and dimensions, it is possible to use the questionnaires developed and used during the ACTION project. They are available at the following link on [Zenodo](#). Some questionnaires have been adapted to be used with high-school students. Finally, we include questionnaires to be added as needed to the previous ones for gathering demographic and psychographic information about the citizens/volunteers. Indeed, gathering demographic information is crucial to assess social inclusion, while analysing the psychographic characteristics of participants is useful for considering changes in way of thinking, values and behaviours. It is important to stress that these questionnaires represent a starting point that needs to be adapted in terms of length and language to the needs of each specific project. On the Zenodo it is possible to find also questionnaires in other languages (Spanish, Italian, Norwegian and Portuguese): please note that the translations could be partial compared to the English version as they have been developed for the specific purposes of the ACTION pilots and, for the same reason, in a single questionnaire more than an areas of impact is covered.

In the table that follows we report the questionnaires developed and to whom they should be administered.

Table 2: List of ACTION questionnaires

Title of the questionnaire	To whom it should be administered
Social impact - ex-ante	Citizens
Social impact - ex-ante	Citizen scientists (high school students)
Social impact - ex-post	Citizens
Social impact - ex-post	Citizen (high school students)
Social impact - ex-post	CS managers
Economic impact - ex-post	CS managers
Political impact - ex-ante	CS managers
Political impact - ex-ante	Citizen
Political impact - ex-post	CS managers
Political impact - ex-post	Citizen
Transformative potential tool	CS managers
Demographic and personal information	Citizen (adults)
Demographic and personal information	Citizen (high school students)
Psychographic information articulated in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Environmental issues and green behaviours ● Self-perceived efficacy and social desirability ● Vision toward science 	Citizen (adults)
Psychographic information declined in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Environmental issues and green behaviours ● Self-perceived efficacy and social desirability ● Vision toward science 	Citizen (high school students)

3 CS project sustainability

Assessing the impact of a CS project can help increase its sustainability: for example by providing funding agencies and policy makers with qualitative and quantitative information on the benefits produced by the project, in this way supporting their need for information for deciding on eventual additional fundings. It can also help during a fundraising campaign, in motivating people in contributing to a project that shows positive impacts at different levels.

However, working towards financial sustainability, asks for more than an impact assessment. On this, it is important to say that there is not a solution that fits all CS projects but the main recommendation is to consider mixing different approaches to sustainability so as to avoid being dependent on a single source of financing (be it from public or private actors). On this the following sustainability paths have been considered:

- hardware sales,
- subscription models,
- crowd-funding,
- up-scaling funding applications,
- direct donations,
- reframing as science education,
- private funding within the Corporate Social Responsibility framework

As ACTION, we organised two webinars on sustainability and, together with other materials, they can be found in the ACTION toolkit at the following link:

<https://actionproject.eu/toolkit/impact-and-sustainability/>

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provides guidelines on how to assess the impact of a CS project using the ACTION methodology and how to support the long-term financial sustainability of a CS project. The authors are aware that additional support in understanding and applying this methodology can be needed, for this reason the two organisations that developed the methodology, T6 Ecosystem and DRIFT, will remain available for providing such support for the next two years (up to January 2024). The authors can be, therefore, contacted at the following email addresses:

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REFERENCES

Passani, A., Janssen, A.L., Hoelscher, K. (2020), *Impact assessment methodological framework v1*